

Solid Waste Management of Binpur II Block, Jhargram, West Bengal

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Abstract

Managing solid waste has become a significant concern in both urban and rural areas of India. This issue poses a challenge for authorities in developing nations due to the high rate of waste production. The development and lifestyle changes in urban areas attract people from rural regions, leading to the generation of village solid waste. The rapid pace of industrialization and technological advancements in society contributes to the high rate of waste generation. Waste produced in rural areas significantly contributes to environmental pollution, including air, water, and soil contamination. Nowadays, this issue is not confined to urban areas but also affects villages. Therefore, it is crucial to take immediate action to address these challenges. This study aims to evaluate the practices and understanding related to the collection and disposal of household solid waste in the rural area of Binpur II block, located in the Jhargram District of West Bengal. According to the 2011 census, the population of Binpur II block is approximately 164,522. Currently, the block lacks an adequate system for waste collection and disposal. Therefore, this research seeks to explore the current situation of solid waste generation in the block, along with findings and recommendations for its effective collection and disposal. This study showed that the respondents were not systematic in planning the processes involved in the production, processing, and utilization of organic waste. The main method for managing organic waste is through composting. A community-based study was conducted on randomly chosen families residing in the Binpur II block. Random samples of waste were collected from households and weighed to estimate the total waste produced by an average family in the block. The results in these categories were analyzed by descriptive statistics and an independent samples T-test using Jamovi software (Version 2.6). The p-values less than 0.05 are considered significant.

Keywords

Solid Waste, Waste Generation, Waste Management.

Introduction

Solid Waste Management (SWM) encompasses the systematic collection, transportation, segregation, processing, and disposal of waste in a scientifically sound manner. It aims to safeguard public health and well-being through balanced economic, environmental, and social appraisals. Recognizing the critical role of SWM in environmental preservation, the Government of India has initiated a series of institutional, legal, and policy-based reforms over the past two decades. A pivotal moment in the evolution of SWM in India occurred in 1998, when the Honourable Supreme Court constituted a high-level committee to assess the condition of waste management systems in metropolitan areas. The committee's report, published in 1999, revealed significant infrastructure and compliance gaps in urban waste governance. In response, the Ministry of Environment and Forests (MoEF), acting on the committee's recommendations, introduced the **Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2000**. These rules mandated urban local bodies (ULBs) to establish comprehensive frameworks for waste storage, collection, segregation, transportation, and disposal. Despite the regulatory framework, widespread non-compliance emerged due to the limited financial, technical, and institutional capacities of ULBs, leaving the objectives of the 2000 Rules largely unmet (Singla, S., 2018).

The growing amount of household waste in rural India is becoming a significant concern. Although most of the solid waste in these areas is organic and biodegradable, it poses a major issue due to the lack of on-site segregation, with daily waste production reaching 0.3 to 0.4 million metric tons, according to the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation (MDWS), Government of India. Careless disposal leads to poor environmental sanitation, which in turn affects the quality of

life. Therefore, it is crucial to manage household waste responsibly. To achieve effective waste management, a proper system must be established. Without an operational waste collection and disposal system at the Panchayat level, it is unreasonable to hold individual households accountable or accuse them of negligence.

To revitalize sanitation and waste management efforts, the Government launched the **Swachh Bharat Mission (SBM)** in 2014. As a successor to the **Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (2009)**, SBM aimed to eliminate open defecation and enhance solid and liquid waste management infrastructure across the country. The Mission was structured in two phases:

Phase I (2014–2019): Focused on building the foundational sanitation infrastructure and declaring areas Open Defecation Free (ODF). **Phase II (2020–2025):** Emphasizes sustainable behavior change, strengthening waste treatment facilities, and comprehensive management of solid and liquid waste. SBM operates under a dual-track approach:

SBM-Gramin, overseen by the Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation (now under the Ministry of Jal Shakti), targets rural sanitation. **SBM-Urban**, managed by the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs, addresses the needs of urban municipalities. The mission strives to ensure no urban or rural community is left behind, and aims to institutionalize ODF behaviors while scaling up waste management interventions in both geographic contexts.

Despite concerted efforts, several systemic issues remain unresolved, particularly in rural India. Public awareness regarding waste and its environmental consequences remains critically low. Open dumping of domestic waste remains a common practice in villages. The rising rural population, growing consumption patterns, and increased commercial activities have led to unprecedented levels of waste generation. According to DDWS-UNICEF (2008), rural India generates approximately 15,000 to 18,000 million liters of greywater per day and 0.3 to 0.4 million metric tonnes of solid waste daily. While rural waste challenges are intensifying, the scale of urban waste production continues to far exceed that of villages, posing a broader set of logistical and infrastructural concerns (Gour, D., 2022). India has made significant progress in framing policies and launching nationwide campaigns to address SWM. However, persistent implementation deficits, especially in rural areas, require targeted investments in infrastructure, public education, and capacity-building to ensure the sustainability and inclusivity of waste management systems.

Objective of study

1. To find out the main source of waste generation in the study area.
2. To estimate the volume of waste generated in the study area.
3. To analyse the solid waste management systems including the waste collection, reuse and processing in this study area.
4. To find out the issues, if any, in the solid waste management process and suggest suitable and scientific mechanisms in dealing the solid waste.
5. To examine the relationship between socio-demographic profile and waste production and management.

Review of Literature

Kadam and Sarawade (2016) focused in their paper on the problems associated with the management of solid waste and the options for treatment in Indian villages and also designing a system to treat solid waste in an environmental friendly approach effectively. They have proposed some solutions for solid waste management at village level, which are: collection and storage of solid waste, segregation and proper treatment and disposal along with the creating awareness among the people.

Singla and Gaba (2018) reviewed in their paper the current method of handling solid waste in the city of Mehsana, Gujarat ranked 22nd in the state of Gujarat and 99th in India by Swachh Sarvekshan 2017, done by Department of drinking water and sanitation under Swachh Bharat mission.

Dheeraj Gour and Saraswat (2022) in their present study endeavors to assess practices and knowledge regarding collection and disposal of household solid waste in the rural community of Jajankhedi Village located in Sehore District of Madhya Pradesh.

They investigated that there is no proper waste collection and disposal system in the village. Hence, as mentioned earlier, this study is done to discuss the present scenario of solid waste generation in the village along with findings and suggestions for its proper collection and disposal. It was observed that the percentage of organic waste in the samples is higher as compared to other waste categories. Looking at the factor, vermin composting technology is proposed so that organic waste can be utilized in manure production. This will also help in generating revenue for the Gram Panchayat as the manure formed can be easily sold in the open market

Liji Samuel (2020) observed that Proper scientific mechanisms are not available in disposing of the wastes generated by the different economic sectors in the study area of Kalayapuram, a small Village/hamlet in Vettikkavala Block in Kollam District of Kerala State, India.

In their 2023 study, **Syafrudin, S. et al.** noted that the waste output from the southern region of Gunungkidul Regency in Indonesia is similar to that of many rural areas in developing nations. They determined that the average waste production was 0.29 kilograms per person each day, classifying the area as a small town in terms of waste generation. Food waste and leaves made up 75% of the solid waste, while paper, plastic, glass, wood, other materials, and fabrics accounted for 11.8%, 10.1%, 1.7%, 0.5%, 0.5%, and 0.4%, respectively. The high density of 110.6 kilograms per cubic meter indicated that residential areas produced less recyclable waste. Factors such as economic activity, lifestyle, geographic conditions, and the appeal of the downtown area influenced the waste generation and composition.

Hypothesis

1. H01: There is no significant difference between Education and Organic Waste.
H11: There is significant difference between Education and Organic Waste.
2. H02: There is no significant difference between Income and Drainage system of house.
H12: There is significant difference between Income and Drainage system of house.
3. H03: There is no significant difference between Family size and Food waste produced at home.
H13: There is significant difference between Family size and Food waste produced at home.
4. H04: There is no significant difference between Occupation and Cooking waste produced at home.
H14: There is significant difference between Occupation and Cooking waste produced at home.
5. H05: There is no significant difference between Caste and Cooking waste like ashes produced at home.
H15: There is significant difference between Caste and Cooking waste like ashes produced at home.
6. H06: There is no significant difference between Crop Residues and Cooking waste like ashes produced at home.
H16: There is significant difference between Crop Residues and Cooking waste like ashes produced at home.

Methodology

The present study will be based on primary and secondary data. The primary data will be collected from various classes of people who are likely to be selected randomly as respondents. Through interviews with daily wage labourers, farmers, rickshaw and van pullers, toto and car drivers, businessmen, students, jobholders, and housewives, the requisite relevant information will be collected to assess the exact condition of solid waste management with direct field observation. Primary data will also be collected from the waste collection process or and the selected dumping area. For taking expert opinion on the key points, an interview will be conducted with the various stakeholders who are experts in solid waste management practice in this district. Secondary data will be collated from Gram Panchayat, block office, books, journals, magazines, etc.

Binpur II is a community development block that forms an administrative division in the Jhargram subdivision of Jhargram district in the Indian state of West Bengal. According to the 2011 Census of India, Binpur II CD block had a total population of 164,522, of which 158,798 were rural and 5,724 were urban. There were 82,654 (50%) males and 81,868 (50%) females. The population in the age range 0–6 years was 19,354. Scheduled Castes numbered 25,947 (15.77%) and Scheduled Tribes numbered 65,722 (39.95%). From this block, 61 respondents are randomly selected for data collection. The questionnaires were developed referring to earlier studies conducted in the relevant field.

The results in these categories were analyzed by descriptive statistics and an independent samples T-test using Jamovi software (Version 2.6) [Computer Software]. The p-values less than 0.05 are considered significant.

Research Question:

1. How many types of waste are found in this area?
2. Which type of waste is found in the maximum amount in this area?
3. How can rural people manage their waste?
4. Where have the wastes been discharged?
5. What are the Government's steps in rural waste management?

Study Area:

Binpur II is a community development block that serves as an administrative division within the Jhargram subdivision of the Jhargram district in the Indian state of West Bengal.

The Chota Nagpur Plateau gradually descends, resulting in a hilly terrain characterized by infertile laterite rocks and soil. In the Binpur II CD block, 95% of the cultivated land consists of lateritic soil, while the remaining 5% comprises alluvial soil. The Binpur II CD block is susceptible to drought, experiencing particularly severe drought conditions. Belpahari is situated at 22°31'56"N 86°38'45"E.

The Binpur II CD block is bordered to the north by the Raipur and Ranibandh CD blocks in the Bankura district, to the east by the Binpur I CD block, to the south by the Jamboni CD block and the Ghatshila CD block in the Purvi Singhbhum district of Jharkhand, and to the west by the Bandwan CD block in the Purulia district. It is situated 53 kilometers from Midnapore, which serves as the district headquarters.

The Binpur II CD block encompasses an area of 583.50 km². It comprises 1 panchayat samity, 10 gram panchayats, 128 gram sansads (village councils), 470 mouzas, and 401 inhabited villages. The block is served by the Belpahari and Binpur police stations.[9] The administrative headquarters of this CD block is located in Belpahari.

As of the 2005-06 period, Binpur II CD block had a forest cover of 13,694 hectares, within a total geographical area of 57,574 hectares. The gram panchayats within the Binpur II block/panchayat samiti include Banspahari, Bhulaveda, Kanko, Shimulpal, Belpahari, Ergoda, Sandapara, Bhelaidiha, Harda, and Shilda.

According to the 2011 Census of India, the total population of Binpur II CD block was 164,522, with 158,798 individuals residing in rural areas and 5,724 in urban settings. The population consisted of 82,654 males (50%) and 81,868 females (50%). The number of individuals aged 0-6 years was 19,354. The Scheduled Castes accounted for 25,947 individuals (15.77%), while the Scheduled Tribes numbered 65,722 (39.95%). The census town within Binpur II CD block is Shilda, with a population of 5,724 according to the 2011 census.

Villages within Binpur II CD block, along with their respective populations from the 2011 census, include: Belpahari (1,863), Banspahari (1,402), Bhula Bheda (961), Simulpal (1,171), Sondapara (1,219), Bheladiha (207), Kanko (1,124), Ergoda (1,408), and Harda (2,627).

As per the 2011 census, the total count of literate individuals in the Binpur II CD block was 102,285, which constitutes 70.46% of the population aged over 6 years. Among these, the male population was recorded at 58,804, representing 80.79% of the male demographic over 6 years, while the female population stood at 43,481, accounting for 60.07% of the female demographic over 6 years. The disparity in literacy rates between genders was noted to be 20.72%. In the same census, the Hindu population was 121,224, making up 73.68% of the total population in the Binpur II CD block. The Muslim population was recorded at 1,220, which is 0.74% of the total population. Additionally, the category labeled as 'Others' comprised 42,078 individuals, representing 25.58% of the population. This 'Others' category includes various communities such as Addi Bassi, Marang Boro, Santal, Saranath, Sari Dharma, Sarna, Alchchi, Bidin, Sant, Saevdharm, Seran, Saran, Sarin, Kheria, Christians, and other religious groups. In the 2001 census, the proportions were 60.29% for Hindus, 0.59% for Muslims, and 38.68% for tribal religions within the population. At the time of the 2011 census, 71.61% of the population reported Bengali as their first language, while 25.27% spoke Santali and 2.71% communicated in Kurmali.

West Bengal in India
Binpur II Block in Jhargram District

Binpur II Block, Jhargram, West Bengal

Sl. No.	QUESTIONS	YES	NO
1	DO you have toilet at home?	54 (88.5%)	7 (11.5%)
2	Is there any pit?	19 (31.1%)	42(68.9%)
3	Is there manure pit?	48(78.7%)	13(21.3%)
4	Do organic waste (Food waste etc) in home	60(98.4%)	1(1.6%)
5	Do metallic waste produced at home	27(44.3%)	34(55.7%)
6	Do cooking waste like ashes produced at home	50(82%)	11(18%)
7	Do paper / cotton type waste produced at home?	55(90.2%)	6(9.8%)
8	Do plastic waste produced at home	58(95.1%)	3(4.9%)
9	Does e-waste (batteries, electrical, electronic wastes) produce at home?	52(85.2%)	9(14.8%)
10	Do livestock faeces produced at home?	47(77%)	14(23%)
11	Is biomedical waste produced at home?	19(31.1%)	42(68.9%)
12	Are crop residues produced at home?	46(75.4%)	15(24.6%)
13	Is Chemical waste (like paints etc.) Produced at home?	5(8.2%)	56(91.8%)
14	Does the local panchayet / municipality collect waste?	9(14.8%)	52(85.2%)
15	Does the village have common organic waste management system?	11(18.3%)	49(81.7%)
16	Does the village have common organic waste management plant/site?	9(14.8%)	52(85.2%)
17	Is the waste segregated to bio-degradable / non-bio-degradable at home?	14(23%)	47(77%)

Source: Primary Data, percentage within the bracket

Null Hypothesis- 1

There is no significant difference between Education and Organic Waste.

Table- 2

DO ORGANIC WASTE PRODUCED AT HOME?			
Education	Yes	No	Total
Never went to school	5 (8.2%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (8.2%)
Primary	17 (27.9%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (27.9%)
MP/HS	26 (42.6%)	0 (0.0%)	26 (42.6%)
Graduate	10 (16.4%)	0 (0.0%)	10 (16.4%)
PG/PhD	1 (1.6%)	1 (1.6%)	2 (3.3%)
Professional	1 (1.6%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (1.6%)
Total	60 (98.4%)	1 (1.6%)	61 (100%)

N=61, $\chi^2= 30.0$, df= 5, p value= <0.001 Significant at 0.01 level

According to Table No. 2, the result is significant. It means there is significant association between Education and the Organic waste produced at home per day. The study indicates that the increase of education level, the production of organic waste is decreased. Here we see, people who MP/HS passed generates more waste that others which is 42.6% of total respondents. On the other hand, PG/PhD and professional degree holders (1.6%) generates least amount of organic waste.

Null Hypothesis- 2

There is no significant difference between Income and Drainage system of house

Table- 3

Income	Drainage system of House						Total
	Proper cover drain	Open drain	Septic pit	Outlet into water bodies	Non-metal drain	No drainage	
Below 10k	-	4 (14.8%)	-	1 (3.7%)	13 (48.1%)	9 (33.3%)	27 (100%)
10k-20k	-	11 (50%)	-	0 (0%)	9 (40.9%)	2 (9.1%)	22 (100%)
20k-30k	-	4 (50%)	1 (12.5%)	1 (12.5%)	2 (25%)	0 (0%)	8 (100%)
30k-40k	1 (25%)	2 (50%)	-	-	1 (25%)	-	4 (100%)
Total	1 (1.6%)	21 (34.4%)	1 (1.6%)	2 (3.3%)	25 (41%)	11 (18%)	61 (100%)

N= 61, $\chi^2= 37.0$, df= 15, p value= <0.001 Significant at 0.01 level

According to Table No. 3, the result is significant. It means there is significant association between Income and Drainage System of houses. Most of Poor-income-level families (48.1%) have no drainage where maximum higher-income-level families (25%) have proper covered drainage. In this study maximum family have Non-Metal drain (41%) and open drain (34.4%). A few numbers of family (1.6%) have own septic pit.

Null Hypothesis- 3

There is no significant difference between Family size and Food waste produced at home

Table- 4

Family size	Food waste produced at home						Total
	Below 100g	100-200g	200-300g	300-400g	400-500g	Above 500g	
Nuclear (2-4)	1 (1.6%)	1 (1.6%)	3 (4.9%)	6 (9.8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	11 (18%)
Extended (5-6)	0 (0%)	1 (1.6%)	1 (1.6%)	12 (19.7%)	20 (32.8%)	2 (3.3%)	36 (59%)
Joint (Above 6)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (3.3%)	4 (6.6%)	8 (13.1%)	14 (23%)
Total	1 (1.6%)	2 (3.3%)	4 (6.6%)	20 (32.8%)	24 (39.3%)	10 (16.4%)	61 (100%)

N= 61, $\chi^2= 43.8$, df= 10, p value= <0.001 Significant at 0.01 level

As the result is significant above table (Table No. 4), that means there is a relation between family size and food waste produced at home per day. Here we see in the study, the increase of family size the quantity of food waste is increased. Most of nuclear family (9.8%) generate 300-400g or less amount of food waste. 32.8% Extended family produced more than 300-400g food waste. And maximum number of joint family (13.1%) produced above 500g food waste per day.

Null Hypothesis- 4

There is no significant difference between Occupation and Cooking waste produced at home

Table- 5

Occupation	Cooking Waste Produced at home		Total
	Yes	No	
Farming	11 (18%)	-	11 (18%)
Business	6 (9.8%)	-	6 (9.8%)
Govt Job	2 (3.3%)	5 (8.2%)	7 (11.5%)
Private Job	5 (8.2%)	2 (3.3%)	7 (11.5%)
Driver	7 (11.5%)	-	7 (11.5%)
Student	5 (8.2%)	1 (1.6%)	6 (9.8%)
Housewives	9 (14.8%)	1 (1.6%)	10 (16.4%)
Others	5 (8.2%)	2 (3.3%)	7 (11.5%)
Total	50 (82%)	11 (18%)	61 (100%)

N= 61, $\chi^2= 20.3$, df= 7, p value= 0.005, Significant at 0.01 level

According to Table No. 5, the result is significant. It means there is significant association between occupation and cooking waste produced at home per day. In this study we observed that farmers' family (18%) produced more cooking waste than others. Only the Govt. job holders' family (3.3%) generates less amount of cooking waste like ashes because their good financial condition.

Null Hypothesis- 5

There is no significant difference between Caste and Cooking waste like ashes produced at home

Table- 6

Caste	Cooking waste like ashes produced at home		Total
	Yes	No	
GEN	15 (24.6%)	4 (6.6%)	19 (31.1%)
SC	9 (14.8%)	2 (3.3%)	11 (18%)
ST	21 (34.4%)	-	21 (34.4%)
OBC-A	2 (3.3%)	-	2 (3.3%)
OBC-B	3 (4.9%)	5 (8.2%)	8 (13.1%)
Total	50 (82%)	11 (18%)	61 (100%)

N= 61, $\chi^2= 15.9$, df= 4, p value= 0.003, Significant at 0.01 level

In the above table (table no 6), we found that there is a relation between caste and cooking waste produced. Changes in cooking waste like ashes production can be observed with the changes in caste. ST categories are produced highest cooking waste like ashes which is 34.4% from total respondents, and OBC-A and OBC-B categories are produced minimum cooking waste like ashes which is 3.3% and 4.9% respectively.

Null Hypothesis- 6

There is no significant difference between Crop Residues and Cooking waste like ashes produced at home

Table- 7

Crop Residues	Cooking waste like ashes produced at home		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	42 (68.9%)	4 (6.6%)	46 (75.4%)
No	8 (13.1%)	7 (11.5%)	15 (24.6%)
Total	50 (82%)	11 (18%)	61 (100%)

N= 61, $\chi^2= 11.0$, df= 1, p value= <0.001, Significant at 0.01 level

According to Table No. 7, the result is significant. So, we say that there is a relation between crop residues and cooking waste produced at home. Out of the total 61 respondents in the study area, 42 (68.9%) respondents generate crop residues and cooking waste like ashes both from their home daily. 18% respondent do not produce crop residues and cooking waste like ashes. In this table we observed that when the crop residue increases of a household, the amount of cooking waste increases this household and crop residues decreased then cooking waste like ashes also decreased.

Findings

1. Organic waste is generated in bulk quantity in the study area. Every household generates around 300- 400g of organic waste daily in the study area.
2. 88.5% of the households in this study area have toilet facilities. Most homes here do not have septic pits, with only 31.1% of homes having this system.
3. 78.7% of households here have manure pits. 98.4% of respondents in the study area produce food waste daily.
4. 44.3% of households in this study area generate metal waste every day. Cooking waste like ashes is produced by 82% of households in this study area every day.
5. In this study area, 95.1%, 85.2%, 31.1%, and 8.2% of the respondents produce plastic waste, e-waste, bio-medical waste, and chemical waste daily, respectively.
6. Crop residues and livestock excrement are generated daily from 75.4% and 77% of respondents' homes, respectively.
7. Local governments collect waste from only 14.8% of households daily or every few days. In this study area, 23% of respondents segregate their biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste into separate categories.
8. According to the data available here, 18.3% of total respondent says that they have a common organic waste management system. There is no waste management plant in this study area. Only Shilda under Shilda Panchayat has a waste dumping site where solid waste is collected and burn at intervals of a few days.
9. It was clear that in this study areas of production, processing, and utilization of organic waste, there was a lack of systematic planning among the respondents. Composting is the main management process of organic waste.

Conclusion

As the majority of the people are still living in rural areas, the Indian Government have to take some serious steps to address the problem of solid waste management. At present, there is no working solid waste management mechanism in Binpur II block, Jhargram. The waste from households is thrown in the open grounds. The major content of the waste being generated is organic waste. Every household in the study area generates approximately 300-400g of organic waste daily. Since organic content is generated in bulk quantity, it can be utilized for making compost which will also contribute in generating revenue for the Gram Panchayat. Considering all the important factors, it was concluded that Vermi-composting technology is best suited for generating compost. The quality of compost formed by this process is much superior as compared to compost formed with the help of other technologies. As the practice of organic farming is increasing, vermin-compost technology is the best-suited among all sustainable practices. Vermi-compost is rich in nutrient content and this may be a good asset for sustainable agriculture. Vermi-composting also improves the physical characteristics of soil. Development of this method will also help farmers to prepare itself and low-cost fertilizer from their agricultural waste. The proposed technique will take care of all the organic waste generated in households & leftover waste from farming and will also help in generating revenue for the village. The revenue generation calculation sheet is also enclosed.

The key recommendations that arose from this research include:

1. For effective and scientific management of the solid waste in rural the focus should be on management at household level. If the management is not possible at household level, the management should be done at the community level. The motivation of community members is crucial. Engage local leaders and educational institutions to raise community awareness.
2. In the study area, as the major portion is of organic waste, composting facility is a good option for solid waste processing.
3. Segregation of biodegradable and non-biodegradable solid waste at the household level is needed. Reuse of non-biodegradable waste at the household level to the possible extent.
4. 4'R' like Reduce, Reuse, Recycle and Recovery must apply to the study area.
5. Establish designated collection centres for the sorting of plastics, glass, and metals. Collaborate with local recycling firms to facilitate the periodic transportation of sorted waste. Advocate for alternatives such as cloth bags, leaf

- plates, and clay pots. Organize workshops focused on effective waste segregation and disposal.
6. Government intervention is necessary to address the issues. The government have to start focusing on door-to-door collection. Utilize SMS or mobile applications to plan and monitor waste collection schedules.
 7. Identify the infamous spots which are prone to waste disposal. Local government has to identify that and educate the people not to throw waste in this empty space.
 8. As the primary collection of waste, private agencies and NGOs have to be involved.
 9. It is imperative to amend and implement legislation concerning waste disposal and management systems.
 10. Train and hire young individuals as waste collectors, sorters, and composting facilitators. Utilize initiatives such as the Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) for financial support and resources.
 11. As the major portion of the organic waste, composting facility is a very good option for solid waste management. Create community composting sites or individual compost bins utilizing cow dung, kitchen scraps, and dry leaves

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